

**IMPROVING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF THE LABOR
FORCE IN THE LABOR MARKET**

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The development of the national labor market of Uzbekistan consists of ensuring reasonable employment of the population and its regulation, as well as forming a qualified labor market, which is an important and integral component of the labor market, improving the system of training personnel for professions, training personnel for professions, etc.

At this point, as the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev noted: “The fact that 50 percent of school graduates enter the labor market without having any profession should make us all think. Therefore, it is necessary to effectively use the opportunities of more than 700 vocational schools, colleges and technical schools.

For this purpose, a new program will be implemented from 2023. European vocational education standards are introduced in 1 technical school in each region. In the next five years, all colleges and technical schools will be covered by this system”¹.

Today's global economic development, in order to properly confront the threats and risks of various financial and economic crises, to prevent its negative impact on the economy. created the need to train competitive specialists. The training of qualified personnel is carried out in the higher, professional education system, vocational schools that prepare personnel, in the secondary special education system, and in special training courses, and in direct production. This includes the development of the education system on the basis of the Law “On Education”, the Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On additional measures to further improve the professional education system” and “On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030”, as well as the training of qualified personnel in our country. allowing the strengthening of the system.

¹ Referral of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis and the people of Uzbekistan. “Xalq so’zi” newspaper, December 21, 2022, 272 (8334).

Figure 1. Expected duration of education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, years²

The expected length of education in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2014 was 12.5 years, in 2017 it was 13.0 years, and in 2021 it was 14.0 years, and compared to 2014, it increased by +1.5 years in 2021 (Figure 1).

Vocational colleges and higher education institutions of our country train significantly more specialists in some professions and specialties compared to the real demand in the labor market, and in other professions and specialties, they are training so few specialists that they cannot meet the demand of the labor market.

At the beginning of the 2000-2001 academic year, the number of higher education institutions in the Republic of Uzbekistan was 61, and foreign higher education institutions did not operate. In this academic year, the number of students in higher education institutions per 10,000 population was 74, and the number of specialists who graduated from higher education institutions was 31,600. At the beginning of the 2021-2022 academic year, the number of higher education institutions in our republic increased to 154, including the number of operating foreign higher education institutions by 25. In the 2021-2022 academic year, the number of students in higher education institutions per 10,000 inhabitants increased by 229, and the number of specialists who graduated from higher education institutions increased by 103,900 (Table 1).

² It was developed by the author based on the information of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Table 1

The number of higher education organizations of the Republic of Uzbekistan³

Key indicators	2000	2003	2006	2009	2012	2015	2018	2021
	/ 2001	/ 2004	/ 2007	/ 2010	/ 2013	/ 2016	/ 2019	/ 2022
Олий таълим ташкилотлари сони, бирлик	61	62	64	66	64	69	98	154
Including foreign higher education institutions	-	2	3	6	6	7	10	25
Students in higher education institutions corresponding to 10,000 population	74	99	107	103	86	84	110	229
Thousands of specialists who graduated from higher education institutions	31,6	45,5	60,7	71,8	60,9	66,3	70,3	103,9

Abandonment of the administrative and command methods of providing and managing the national economic sectors with qualified personnel has led to the need to move to more organized means and forms of influencing the personnel potential corresponding to market relations.

Employment of the population is one of the indicators of successful economic reforms. The policy of our independent state, the current level of development of

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our society, culture, science and technology, the penetration of the market economy, the new issues facing higher education are not only qualitatively new content and teaching in technology, but also the demand for specialists who understand the laws of the market economy and to determine the directions of their training. It also requires a new approach. This means that success in the development of the economy is determined by the quality dimensions of personnel training and the availability of a qualitatively new workforce. It is becoming extremely important to create a mechanism for state management of training of highly educated personnel at the state level, their employment, increasing the employment of the population and other processes. This requires that the plan of admission of students to higher educational institutions of the country is fully in line with the real demand of national economic sectors.

The analysis of the experience of the USA, Germany, Japan, France and other countries with the most developed economies and intellectual development showed that the high quality and competitiveness of personnel training at all levels is ensured by:

- interdependence of education, science and production;
- variety of educational institutions and vocational training programs developed on the basis of the latest achievements of science, technology, technology and economy;
- turning the vocational education system into a priority and highly profitable sector of the economy;
- providing educational institutions with modern educational and methodological literature, attracting highly qualified teachers and specialists to the vocational education system;
- computerization and informatization of the educational process;
- use of objective quality control and evaluation systems of personnel training;
- conducting psychological-pedagogical research on problems of development, measurement and assessment of thinking, abilities and personal qualities, as well as professional orientation;
- ensuring a high level of material and social protection of teachers.

At the core of a competitive personnel training strategy is an integrated approach to three main cycles of quality assurance:

At the first stage, staffing needs are forecasted and requirements for them are determined, i.e. staffing model is created, progressive high level of quality is determined.

At the second stage, training of qualified personnel is carried out, which should ensure the specified quality level.

In the third stage, the stage related to the use of qualified personnel in the field of professional activity, the level of quality ensured should be regularly increased.

– based on this, the main components of improving the quality and competitiveness of personnel training in accordance with the above-mentioned strategy and experience of the most economically developed and intellectually advanced countries and improving the system of qualified personnel training in accordance with the structural changes in the economy are the following:

– the state policy in the field of training of qualified personnel is the formation of well-rounded individuals-citizens through the continuous education system, which is inextricably linked with the intellectual, spiritual and moral education of a person;

– based on accurate and complete information about future potential labor supply (graduates of educational institutions, professional education, vocational colleges, lyceum, school graduates, etc.) jobs should be created;

– guarantors of the implementation and development of the system of qualified personnel training in the state and society, acting as a coordinator of the activities of highly qualified competitive specialists;

– realizing the rights of citizens to get education, choose a profession, improve their qualifications;

– providing qualified personnel training institutions with modern educational, scientific and methodological literature in Uzbek language, as well as material and technical base;

– creating the necessary conditions for the formation of a socially active, spiritually rich person and the training of highly qualified competitive personnel in continuous educational activities;

– international exchange of national achievements and personnel to solve the most important problems of modern science and technology;

– use of advanced and comprehensive educational standards developed on the basis of international standards using modern science, technical achievements, technologies;

– increasing the training of highly qualified scientific and pedagogical personnel;

- retraining of teachers on the basis of modern knowledge and achievements, taking into account the structural and quality reforms of institutions that train qualified personnel;
- improvement of model plans and programs for subjects taking into account the use of the latest pedagogical, information, computer and other technologies in the process of personnel training;
- developing and implementing a scientifically based system of measuring and evaluating the quality of training of qualified personnel at all levels;
- creation of the infrastructure to support the personnel training process in terms of scientific research;
- formation and development of the information base on various fields of knowledge in order to use educational information networks;
- increase the quality of training of highly qualified personnel, comprehensive support of the scientific talent of young people;
- development of a career guidance system that helps people choose the most appropriate type of employment, taking into account the requirements, opportunities and socio-economic situation of the labor market, as well as supports the abilities of talented young people;
- effective use of the potential of education, science and production in training of competitive personnel within the framework of integrated educational institutions for branch and regional economy;
- to activate the integration of the country's science in the international scientific community, to strengthen the process of exchange of scientific achievements and experience with scientists in order to improve the field of education and personnel training;
- formation of the direction and level of personnel training system based on production needs;
- to expand the forms and methods of training specialists with higher professional education from among personnel with secondary specialized education;
- improving the financing mechanism of educational institutions and bringing it to the level of economically developed and intellectually developed countries;
- reproduction of competitive personnel potential of the republic due to retraining of working personnel of various levels and unemployed specialists;
- development of qualification rates of personnel at all levels before labor market requirements are formed;

development and improvement of targeted training of personnel at all levels.

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